

Entomological Origin of Honey Discriminated by NMR Chloroform Extracts in Ecuadorian Honey

P. Vit, J. Uddin, V. Zuccato, F. Maza, E. Schievano

Abstract—Honeys are produced by *Apis mellifera* and stingless bees (Meliponini) in Ecuador. We studied honey produced in beeswax combs by *Apis mellifera*, and honey produced in pots by *Geotrigona* and *Scaptotrigona* bees. Chloroform extracts of honey were obtained for fast NMR spectra. The 1D spectra were acquired at 298 K, with a 600 MHz NMR Bruker instrument, using a modified double pulsed field gradient spin echoes (DPFGSE) sequence. Signals of ^1H NMR spectra were integrated and used as inputs for PCA, PLS-DA analysis, and labelled sets of classes were successfully identified, enhancing the separation between the three groups of honey according to the entomological origin: *A. mellifera*, *Geotrigona* and *Scaptotrigona*. This procedure is therefore recommended for authenticity test of honey in Ecuador.

Keywords—*Apis mellifera*, honey, ^1H NMR, entomological origin, Meliponini.

I. INTRODUCTION

HONEY is the sweet product extracted from combs by *Apis* species and from pots by Meliponini species of bees in the world [1]. Meliponiculture is the art to keep stingless bees. “Stinglessness seems rather sensational” although it does not refer to a lack of sting, but to a modified non-functional sting [2]. These bees of the Meliponini Tribe live in the tropics, and their honeys processed in cerumen pots were enjoyed before Columbus as *Apis mellifera* was introduced later [3].

In a human/animal interface study Aboriginal honey hunting in Australia is reviewed [4]. Domesticating stingless bee feral colonies in hives still needs strategies that facilitate the location of nests, and that also facilitate honey harvest [4,5].

P. Vit was with Universidad de Los Andes, Mérida, Venezuela. She is now Prometeo Researcher with the Universidad Técnica de Machala, El Oro province, Ecuador, and Honorary Associate at The University of Sydney, NSW, Australia (corresponding author phone: 0593 992623622; e-mail: vitolivier@gmail.com).

J. Uddin is with the Università di Padova, Italia (e-mail: jalal.uddin@studenti.unipd.it).

V. Zuccato, is with Università di Padova, Italia. (e-mail: valentina.zuccato@gmail.com).

F. Maza with the Universidad Técnica de Machala, El Oro province, Ecuador (e-mail: wmaza@utmachala.edu.ec).

E. Schievano is with the Università di Padova, Italia, Italia (e-mail: elisabetta.schievano@unipd.it).

Networking between stingless bee keepers is an indicator of success to multiply colonies and marketing of pot-honey [5]. In a Mexican survey with Mayan stingless bees, *Melipona beecheii* showed colony loss caused by abundance of Africanized honey bee, or beekeeping experience was lower than that caused by competition for food [6]. The Brazilian large-scale survey to support and improve meliponiculture by a quantitative approach and analysis, offers a solid basis needed to increase economic profits of stingless bee products, especially pot-honey [5]. Four key roles are highlighted here to explain why Brazilian Government officers in the tropics are interested to develop the stingless bee industry by promoting: 1. Their local biodiversity, 2. Their economic importance for the role as pollinators in natural flora and commercial crops, 3. The fact that lack of stings facilitates management, 4. Easier manipulation of smaller hives than *Apis mellifera*, demanding technical skills instead of physical strength, accessible to children, women, elderly unable to care for an apiary by themselves.

Standards of pot-honey have not been created [7]. The *Codex Alimentarius Commission* international honey standards for honey are designed for *Apis mellifera* only [8]. Only the Colombian Honey Norm has included an annex with quality chemical factors of pot-honey [9]. Needs of chemical markers to authenticate the entomological origin have been approached by multivariate analysis of fructose, glucose and maltose [10], physic-chemical quality factors [11], sensory Free Choice Profile (FCP) [12], NMR and chemometrics [13], flavonoid C-glycosides [14] and O-glycosyl flavones [15], and more recently by electrophoretic patterns because different species of stingless bees produce honey with distinctive protein bands [16].

Pot-honey is known to be consumed either for family use or to reach up to 1,100% the price of *Apis mellifera* honey [17]. This great difference is a motivation to declare a false entomological origins, causing an Economically Motivated Adulteration (EMA), to be added to the four types of EMAs causing vulnerabilities in the US honey market: 1. Dilution with syrups, 2. Feeding sugar to bees during nectar offer, 3. Masking countries of origin, and 4. Antibiotic residues after excessive veterinary doses [18]. Therefore the importance to certify the entomological origin of honey.

In this work, ^1H NMR on chloroform extracts of honey were used to discriminate between the entomological origin of honey produced by *Apis mellifera* and pot-honey produced by the genera *Geotrigona* and *Scaptotrigona*.

II. METHODS

A. Honey Samples

Ecuadorian commercial honeys from three entomological origins *Apis mellifera*, *Geotrigona* and *Scaptotrigona* were collected during field work, and kept frozen until analysis.

B. Chloroform Extract of Honey

A water:chloroform mixture (1:1) was used as extractive solvent to discard sugars –the major compounds of honey, retained in the water phase. The aroma compounds and other hydrophobic substances are separated in the organic phase. This extractive procedure yields a concentrated solution adequate for fast NMR analysis. For that purpose, portions of 6.0 ± 0.1 g honey were weighed in a 20 mL capped centrifuge tube and dissolved with 15 mL of deionized water, 15 mL of CHCl_3 were added and the mixture was stirred for 10 min. The biphasic mixture was then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C. The lower chloroform phase was collected in a glass vial and the solvent was evaporated under a gentle stream of nitrogen. The solid residue was dissolved in 600 μL of CDCl_3 and placed in an NMR tube, following the scheme of NMR-based metabolomic approach previously published. Chloroform is a convenient solvent compared to dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and methanol (MeOH) previously used in NMR studies of honey, because the residual chloroform signal is very sharp, in a very small region at 7.26 ppm, which does not overlap with important regions of the spectra [19].

C. ^1H NMR Spectra Acquisition

The 1D spectra were acquired at 298 K, with a 600 MHz

NMR Bruker instrument, using a modified double pulsed field gradient spin echoes (DPFGSE) sequence [20]. This pulse in the DPFGE sequence allows the removal of signals present in the (0-2 ppm) region, required to improve digitization of the weaker peaks, lower integration errors, and also better quantification of the number of resonant spins. The spectra collection, processing and analysis required thirty minutes.

C. Statistical Analysis

Signals of ^1H NMR spectra were integrated and used as inputs for PCA (Principal Component Analysis) and PLS-DA (Partial Least Squares – Discriminant Analysis) analysis [6]. PCA discriminates how one sample is different from another, and identifies the variables contributing to the variation. PLS-DA are based on similar principles as PCA, but additionally labelled sets of classes are identified, enhancing the separation between groups of observations.

III. RESULTS

The spectra of the three entomological origins of honeys studied here (*Apis mellifera*, *Geotrigona*, and *Scaptotrigona*) were compared. The honey produced by these groups of bees share common features and have distinctive regions that merit further analysis. Expanded ^1H -NMR spectra of chloroform extracts of honey produced by these three types of bees, are compared in Fig. 1. A central region (3.5-4.5) ppm is characteristic for each bee type, because it contains the endogenous lipophilic markers, independent of floral and geographical origin. Other substances vary their concentrations.

Fig. 1 Comparison in the expanded region (2.0-5.5 ppm) of ^1H -NMR spectra of chloroform extracts of honeys produced by: 1. *Apis*, 2. *Scaptotrigona*, and 3. *Geotrigona* bees in Ecuador.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Michener, C.D. *The Bees of the World*. 2nd. Baltimore, USA: Ed.The Johns Hopkins University Press, 2007, 992 pp.
- [2] Michener, C.D. "The Meliponini," in *Pot-honey: A legacy of stingless bees*. Vit. P.; Pedro, S.R.M.; Roubik, D., Eds. New York: Springer, 2013, pp. 3-17
- [3] Schwarz, H. Stingless bees (Meliponidae) of the Western Hemisphere. *Bull. Am. Mus. Nat. Hist.* 1948, 90, 1-546.
- [4] Fijn, N. Sugarbag Dreaming: the significance of bees to Yolngu in Arnhem Land, Australia. *H U Ma N I M A L I A* 2014, 6, 1-21.
- [5] Jaffé, R.; Pope, N.; Torres Carvalho, A.; Madureira Maia, U.; Betina Blochtein, B.; Carvalho, C.A.L.; Carvalho-Zilse, G.A.; Magalhães Freitas, B.M.; Menezes, C.; Ribeiro, M.F.; Venturieri, G.C.; Imperatriz-Fonseca V.L. Bees for Development: Brazilian Survey Reveals How to optimize stingless beekeeping. *PLoS One*. 2015; 10(3): e0121157. Published online 2015 Mar 31. doi: 10.1371.
- [6] Villanueva-Gutiérrez, R.; Roubik, D.W.; Colli-Ucán1, W.; Güemez-Ricalde, F.J.; Buchmann, S.L. A Critical View of Colony Losses in Managed Mayan Honey-Making Bees (Apidae: Meliponini) in the Heart of Zona Maya. *J. Kansas Entomol. Soc.*, 2013, 86, 352-362. doi: 10.2317.
- [7] Vit, P. La miel precolombina de abejas sin aguijón (Meliponini) aún no tiene normas de calidad. *Rev. Bol. Centro Investigaciones Biológicas*, 2008, 42, 415-423.
- [8] Instituto Colombiano de ormas Técnicas y Certificación. ICONTEC. NTC 1273. Norma Técnica Colombiana de Miel de Abejas. Bogotá: ICONTEC, 2007. pp. 1-21.
- [9] Codex Alimentarius Commission. CODEX STAN 12. *Norma para la Miel*. Norma adoptada en 1981. Revisiones en 1987 y 2001. Roma: FAO, 1981, pp. 1-8.
- [10] Vit, P., Fernández-Maeso, M.C., Ortiz-Valbuena, A. Potential use of the three frequently occurring sugars in honey to predict stingless bee entomological origin. *J. Applied Entomol.* 1997, 122, 5-8.

PLS-DA

Fig. 2 Principal Component Analysis and PLS-DA on ¹H NMR spectra of chloroform extracts of Ecuadorian honey produced by *Apis mellifera*, and pot-honeys produced by *Geotrigona sp.* and *Scaptotrigona ederi*.

In Fig. 2 the PLS-DA discriminates the three Ecuadorian honey groups according to the entomological origin.

This graphic separation shows more similarities between *Scaptotrigona* and *Apis mellifera* honey, separated only by the second component, because *Geotrigona* honeys are separated from them by the first component.

Besides the recent NMR profiling investigation with 800 honeys originated worldwide [21], the unifloral honeys from Italy [22] and Germany [23], and the entomological and geographical origin prediction [13], this research confirms a new element for denominations of protected origins in honey: The entomological origin, so important in tropical and subtropical ecosystems with stingless bees.

The Australian cosmovision of "Sugarbag Dreaming" connects honey to the knowledge of the surrounding environment and accepted hunting practices in the Northern Territory [4]. Stingless bees, sugarbag structures and honey are conceived in their relationship to humans and other beings as an "indigenous philosophical ecology" [24]. In this way, honey is a complex matrix, and ¹H-NMR one complex method to perceive its chemical composition, adequate to uncover the type of bee originating each honey. Direct observation of the spectra and clusters after integrating NMR signals of honey chloroform extracts by PCA will do that. Therefore, this method is a useful reference for the official agencies and becomes an alternative method for the Ecuadorian Honey Norm [25] to test the entomological origin of Ecuadorian honey, with a biodiversity of 89 stingless bee species in the El Oro, Loja and Zamora Chinchipe provinces in the South of Ecuador [26].

IV. CONCLUSION

The entomological origin of the *Apis mellifera*, and the two major pot-honeys in the Ecuadorian market –*Geotrigona* and *Scaptotrigona ederi*, were successfully discriminated after PLS-DA on ¹H NMR spectra of chloroform honey extracts.

- [11] Vit, P., Persano Oddo, L., Marano, M.L., Salas de Mejías, E. Venezuelan stingless bee honeys characterised by multivariate analysis of compositional factors. *Apidologie*, 1998, 29, 377-389.
- [12] Vit, P., Deliza, R., Pérez, A. How a Huottuja (Piaroa) community perceives genuine and false honey from the Venezuelan Amazon, by free-choice profile sensory method. *Rev. Bras. de Farmacogn.*, 2011, 21, 786-792.
- [13] Schievano, E.; Mammi, S.; Menegazzo, I. "Nuclear Magnetic Resonance as a method for prediction of geographical and entomological origin of pot honey". in *Pot-honey: A legacy of stingless bees*. Vit. P.; Pedro, S.R.M.; Roubik, D., Eds. New York: Springer, 2013, pp. 429-445.
- [14] Truchado, P., Vit, P., Ferreres, F., Tomás-Barberán, F. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry analysis allows the simultaneous characterization of C-glycosyl and O-glycosyl flavonoids in stingless bee honeys. *J. Chromatogr. A*, 2011, 1218, 7601-7607.
- [15] Truchado, P., Vit, P., Heard, T., Tomás-Barberán, F.A., Ferreres, F. Determination of interglycosidic linkages in O-glycosyl flavones by high-performance liquid chromatography/photodiode-array detection coupled to electrospray ionization ion trap mass. Its application to *Tetragonula carbonaria* honey from Australia. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2015, 29, 948-954.
- [16] Ramón-Sierra, J.M., Ruiz-Ruiz, J.C., Ortiz-Vázquez, E.L. Electrophoresis characterisation of protein as a method to establish the entomological origin of stingless bee honeys. *Food Chem.* 2015, 183, 43-48.
- [17] Alves, R.M.O. "Production and marketing of pot-honey". in *Pot-honey: A legacy of stingless bees*. Vit. P.; Pedro, S.R.M.; Roubik, D., Eds. New York: Springer, 2013, pp. 541/556.
- [18] Easter Strayer, S., Everstine, K., Kennedy, S. Economically Motivated Adulteration of Honey: Quality Control Vulnerabilities in the International Honey Market. *FPT* 2014, 34, 8-14.
- [19] Rastrelli, F.; Schievano, E.; Bagnò, A.; Mammi, S. NMR quantification of trace components in complex matrices by band-selective excitation with adiabatic pulses. *Magn. Reson. Chem.* 2009, 47, 868-872.
- [20] Eriksson, L.; Johansson, E.; Kettaneh-Wold, N.; Trygg, J.; Wikström, C.; Wold, S.; Umetrics, A.B.; Umeå, Sweden. 2006. 425 pp.
- [21] Spiteri, M.; Jamin, E.; Thomas, F.; Rebours, A.; Lees, M.; Rogers, K.M.; Rutledge, D.N. Fast and global authenticity screening on honey using ¹H-NMR profiling. *Food Chem.*, 2014 doi:10.1016 (in press).
- [22] Schievano, E.; Stocchero, M.; Morelato, E.; Facchin, C.; Mammi, S. An NMR-based metabolomic approach to identify the botanical origin of honey. *Metabolomics*, 2012, 8, 679-690.
- [23] Ohmenhaeuser, M.; Monakhova, Y.B.; Kuballa, T.; Lachenmeier, D.W. Qualitative and quantitative control of honeys using NMR spectroscopy chemometrics. *Anal. Chem.* 2013, article ID 825318, 1-9 pp. doi:10.1155.
- [24] Instituto Ecuatoriano de Normalización. Norma Miel de Abejas. Requisitos. NTE INEN 1572. Quito: INEN, 1988.
- [25] Ramírez, J.A.; Ureña, J.; Camacho, A. Las abejas sin aguijón de la Región Sur del Ecuador. Loja, Ecuador: Consejo Nacional de Educación Superior, 2013, 85 pp.
- [26] Rose, D. An Indigenous philosophical ecology: Situating the human. *TAJA*, 2009, 16, 294-305.

Patricia Vit was born in Caracas, Venezuela, 20th August 1958. Biology 1981, and MSc Food Science 1984, Universidad Simón Bolívar, Caracas, Venezuela; PhD School of Molecular and Medical Biosciences, University of Wales, Cardiff, UK, 1997. Worked in the Food Science Department, Faculty of Pharmacy and Bioanalysis at Universidad de Los Andes, Mérida, Venezuela 1985-2013.

Honorary Associate at the Sydney School of Medical Sciences, The University of Sydney, Australia since 2011.

She is currently a Prometeo Researcher 2014-2015 at Universidad Técnica de Machala, El Oro province, Ecuador, with the project "Valorization of pot-honey produced by Meliponini in Ecuador". She organized the First Congress of Apiculture and Meliponiculture in Ecuador, Machala, February 2015. Her present challenge is including pre-Columbian pot-honeys in the honey regulations created only for honey produced in combs by *Apis mellifera*. Great effort is done in the ongoing revision of the Ecuadorian honey norm NTE INEN 1572 or in a new norm named "Pot/honey", *Miel de Pote* in Spanish..

Dr. Vit is member of the International Honey Commission (IHC) and the Italo-Latinamerican Society of Ethnomedicine (SILAE). She received the Endeavour Awards Australia 2011, and Academic Awards 2013 Distinction Dr. Mario Picón Salas (First Class) by the Academic Vice Chancellor at Universidad de Los Andes, Venezuela.

Jalal Uddin was born in Karachi, Pakistan, 7th February, 1985. BSc in Chemistry 2005, and MSc Organic Chemistry 2007, University of Karachi, Karachi, Pakistan. Worked as an internee in H.E.J Research Institute of Chemistry, University of Karachi, Karachi, Pakistan 2009-2010.

He is currently a PhD student 2013-2015 in the School of Molecular and Chemical Sciences, with the project based on NMR food metabolomics which is divided into two major subprojects entitled as "NMR based metabolomics approach to identify the botanical and geographical origin of Italian honey" and "Metabolite profiling of rat urine after treatment with antioxidant nutraceutical products, by NMR and Mass Spectrometry".

MSc Jalal Uddin is a member of the Chemical Society of Pakistan (CSP). Currently, he is Erasmus Mundus fellowship holder, funded by the European Union Commission.

Favian Maza was born in Balsas, El Oro province, Ecuador. Superior Technician in Acuicultura, Superior Technical Institute from Guayaquil 1986, Ecuador; Veterinarian Medical Doctor, Universidad Técnica de Machala, Ecuador 1998; Master in Managing Educational and Social Projects, Universidad Técnica de Machala, Ecuador 2002; PhD Candidate in Environmental Science, at Universidad de San Marcos, Lima, Peru,

His interest is to promote and cooperate with scientific research at Universidad Técnica de Machala in Ecuador.

Dr. Maza was Delegate of the National Federation of Veterinaty Medical Doctors representing the El Oro College (2003-2005), and Sub-Dean of the Agrarian and Livestock Faculty (2009-2012). He is currently the Head of the Planning Department and the Official Prometeo Counterpart at Universidad Técnica de Machala, El Oro province, Ecuador. He is Head of the Apiculture and Introduction to Scientific Research Program for students of Veterinary Medicine. Honor Diploma and Golden Medal as best Promotion (1993/1997).

Valentina Zuccato was born in Asaro, Italy. MSc in Industrial Biotechnology in 2011, Università di Padova, Italy.

She is an MSc researcher at Università di Padova working with diverse food matrices such as grape extracts, wine and honey, employing high-resolution NMR coupled to chemometric analysis.

Her scientific interests include Biochemistry, Environmental Biotechnology and Food Science.

Elisabetta Schievano was born in Padova, Italy, October 4th, 1965. Chemistry in 1990, Università di Padova, Italy. CNR Graduate Fellowship (1995-1996), Post Doc Fellowship in Chemistry, Department of Organic Chemistry, Università di Padova (1996-1998). She is a research associate at the Università di Padova since November 1998.

Dr. Schievano scientific interests were in the field of the conformational study of peptides and proteins, with the aim to determine relationships between the biological activity and these secondary structure of molecules by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) methodologies and computational techniques. Recently, her studies focus in the field of Food Science, with interest in diverse food matrices such as olive oil, coffee, milk and cheese, employing high-resolution NMR coupled to chemometric analysis, mass spectrometry and HPLC techniques of food matrices, such as oils, cheese, milk, coffee, honey and more.